

What is visceral writing as a feminist practice?

Working paper for discussion in the research group visceral writing & affect transmission

<https://www.ntnu.edu/isl/visceral-writing>

Nicole Falkenhayner, June 25

The term ‘visceral’ has, in recent years, seen several uses in literary and cultural studies approaches, especially ones that have emerged from the by now solidly explored field of affect studies. As some of the most cited critical authors from the field of affect studies also have explicit feminist, queer, critical race or related critical agendas (cf. Ahmed, Berlant, Brennan, Ngai), it makes sense that the use of the word ‘visceral’ can also be found in related critical contexts. It appears in the titles of academic work connected to performance, art and museum exhibition practices (cf. Akhtari, Nadiminti, Saraf), historical trauma and horror (cf. Belling, Briefel), music composition (cf. Mergenthal), as well as in interpretations of the literary work of specific writers such as, for example, Kathy Acker, Shirley Jackson, or Jeannette Winterson (cf. Chisholm, Antoszek, Bradway). Neethu Khanna explores what she defines as a “visceral logic of decolonisation” to re-read Marxist Indian writing, and in the field of ecofeminist climate fiction, Iris Ralph has observed tropes that express a “visceral ecology of survival” (72). Additionally, the term tends to emerge when systemic effects on marginalised, gendered and racialised bodies come into focus. Another use of the term ‘visceral’ is more embedded in academic work that is linked to phenomenological traditions in literary studies, and from this vantage point addresses visceral readership (cf. Claas) or literacy (cf. Fitzgibbons). Additionally, work on feminist phenomenology and medicine (cf. Shildrick, Zeiler and Folkmarson) should be mentioned. A possible connection to enactivist and cognitive literary studies approaches is also coming into view, last but not least, in the work of some of our group members.

From this unfinished and partial glance at some relevant uses, it can tentatively be stated that

- The term ‘visceral’ has a connection to work in literary and cultural studies emerging from either an affect studies, cognitive literary studies or a phenomenological background.

- It appears to be often, though not exclusively, used in connection with the cultural and literary work of women and/ or literary work articulated from, in various ways, 'feminized' subject positions, so that it appears to be explicitly or implicitly partaking in a radical, or critical, progressive agenda.
- It stresses the embodied constitution of all experience, including the experience of phenomena of oppression, violence, and hurt *through* discourses, which are in themselves, however, not fully disclosable *within* discourses.

While these observations can be seen as the beginning of charting a field in which one encounters the term in our fields (as opposed to, though maybe only on the surface, uses of the term in 'purely' medical academic contexts), it is much more difficult to chart what, exactly, a definition of the use of the term would be. Different authors use it differently for different reasons, and, while in some uses, there is very substantial definition work present (connecting it foundationally with embodied experiences of the enacted mind, for example) others appear to use it rather evocatively, or, as affect has become a much-used term, possibly simply in order to avoid using the latter. However, there seems to be a plethora of experiences that are described as being 'visceral' in nature, as opposed to such which might be described as neutral, rational or only so much as fully defined, and there seem to be artistic, creative, and literary practices that afford visceral reactions to them. By returning to *the use of the term in context with the literary work of specific authors*, as mentioned above, and analyses that connect this to specific affordances and/or aims of specific writing styles and techniques in texts, one can move towards an understanding of 'the visceral', or, as we have also called it, *viscerality* as an aesthetic practice – which means, in my understanding, *viscerality as a poetics or aesthetics*. We would then have to look for which formal features and differences would qualify as instances of this specified poetics and aesthetics, and, possibly following from this, what kinds of *politics* this poetics would potentially be entailing. To tentatively formulate some characteristics of visceral writing in this last sense, these would include, on a purely descriptive basis:

- Techniques and stylistic devices which foreground embodied physical and neurological experiences in ways that break, at least partially, with conventional codes of realist literary fiction, but without (necessarily) seeking recourse to the fantastical, magical, transcendent or otherwise conventionally 'non-realist' modes.
- Rather than the kind of equivalence between non-realist and realist modes of writing established in definitions of, for example, magical realism (cf. Sasser), visceral writing or viscerality operates within an aesthetic field of the 'hyper-real', that means, a technique of mimesis that is aimed at over-stressing the 'actual' reality of embodied, enacted

experience that is not usually fully available to linguistic representation, or that at least breaks with reader expectations in a way that creates disorientation, rupture, vertigo, etc.

- It is not a 'new' phenomenon, but one that is seeing a contemporary resurgence that points towards a possible relationship of contiguity between the literary practices of contemporary (female) writers and developments in theory connected to feminist work in affect studies, ecocriticism, posthumanism. It also shows affiliation with concepts and ideas from the tradition of French feminist theory (cf. Cixous, Kristeva).

However, again in analogy to the history of definitions of magical realism, we should not make the mistake of identifying the formal presence of a visceral aesthetic with an always already radically progressive politics. There might be visceral writing that is written from within and for a regressive, neo-fascist, voyeuristic, etc. agenda, and we would have to think about what we do with such texts. However, from the short and partial overview above, there seems to be strong affiliation of the use of the term from academic perspectives that one might classify as 'feminist' in a broad sense. From my biased perspective, I see visceral strategies emerge in contexts that appear to point towards criticism of something, or the emergence of a language for the vague realisation that something is not quite right, and that this condition of something being amiss is expressed through the focus on the body, bodily states and sense perceptions. As visceral writing often seems to appear concerning the expression of strong emotional or affective experiences that point to either a location deep inside the body (the viscera, the abdominal viscera, the guts, organs that filter, produce and transform, like the liver, the kidneys, and the reproductive organs¹) *and* in contexts which appear to be connected to bodies that are in various ways dis-eased, dis-figured, dis-membered, etc., one could say that *visceral writing is writing that itself enacts a form of mimetic violence*.

What is the 'state of the art' concerning visceral writing – if it exists? A recurring, and connected, question that has emerged in our discussions is the status of the relationship between visceral writing as a style, and visceral affect transmission afforded by texts that are possibly written in this style. If we see the conscious shaping of texts as aimed at affording certain responses to it, we cannot but understand text and response as interconnected, though not necessarily in a controllable, or inducible way. A connected question is: Are we in the process of 'inventing' a concept for which we then search proof, or do we find an observable

¹ I wanted to somehow include organs of sense perception, especially, skin – but as soon as the eyes are a part of the description, I feel like the whole differentiation collapses (as nearly everything in fiction, at least in how my brain works, is somehow 'seen'), so I am still looking for a clever way to deal with this issue. However I wanted to point to the skin specifically because both Christiane and I focused on this in the discussion Sarah Moss's *Ghost Wall*, and Khanna also focuses on the skin.

phenomenon that can be best described in the suggested way? Also, are we operating in a field that has already been charted, and if so, how has it been charted?

Christiane Hansen and I have attempted to tackle this in the research questions for the systematic literature review, work on which is ongoing, in the following way:

- What is the state of the art on the representation and reception of sense perception, affect and somatic experiences in literary fiction by female authors?
- Has the use of these representations and reception effects previously been discussed as a feminist literary practice or strategy, and if so, in which conceptual framework?

We understand the work on the literature review as a first step to chart the field – and possible lacunae in research in which we can productively intervene.

What exactly would distinguish visceral aesthetic practices from affect and/or reader effects, without erasing the resonance of both these heavily researched fields? There might be a possibility here to envision a frame in which cognitive and enactivist approaches might be brought into context with critical theory, aesthetics and political aspects. This might also lead to search for links between contemporary and historical forms of viscerality. Arguably, this might distinguish itself from a divide between form and politics but also create a link between the cognitive sciences / ‘cognitive turn’ literary studies, ‘new formalism’, and key traditions from literary studies, feminist poetic theory traditions, aesthetic studies, and cultural studies. I think the fact that in the group, we come from different traditions of thought and work with different forms of texts in different languages might enable the formulation of a concept that is exact enough to point the figure at an actual phenomenon, but strategically open enough to make a dialogue between different traditions possible.

Why should we define and employ a concept of visceral writing or viscerality as a poetics?

To put forward a grand and unproven claim, it is my intuition that the study of affect has, in certain contexts, been slightly overused by now. However, it seems to me that this is the case mostly in the theoretical field, while using the study of affect as a *method for formal literary analysis* might still yield surprises. It might be that this can be uncovered with a more detailed understanding of visceral writing. This would lead to the following questions:

1. what exactly does it entail to use an affect studies *methodology* (rather than theoretical framework) in literary studies?
2. If we find a way to indeed use the analysis of visceral writing as an expression of an affect studies methodology, then what we call visceral writing (or using a focalisation entailing visceral interiority) might fill a descriptive gap concerning texts that partake in this specific aesthetics. It would enable the formulation of a 'canon' of visceral writing that encompasses both contemporary writers but also opens venues to re-appraise the writing of already canonized writers that partake in this practice, which could potentially lead to uncover unexplored connections in comparative work (for example, Toni Morrison, Clarice Lispector, Shirley Jackson would in my mind all qualify as 'visceral writers', but there are little conventional theoretical perspectives through which their work can be productively compared).
3. A methodological use of visceral writing would close a descriptive gap that leads theoretical affect studies approaches to an affiliation with more formalist analysis
4. How can we show this?

Also, as so much of what, in the *longue durée*, used to 'happen' in textual art forms concerning affect and the visceral has moved variously to audiovisual and interactive media, that appear to be much better equipped at affording affective and visceral reactions than signs on a paper/screen that the mind has to transform into meaning, one might ask if the claimed resurgence of attention to *the visceral in writing* can be seen as a reaction of literary art in the contemporary situation to a transmedia environment that apparently overshadows the textual. This might be framed in the much broader question of what textual art, specifically, *can do* that other media cannot, or not in the same way.

Ahmed, Sara. *The Cultural Politics of Emotion*. NED - New edition, 2 ed., Edinburgh University Press, 2014.

Akhtari, Nazli. "A Visceral and Temporal Remix: Performing Reza Abdoh's Archives." *Theatre Journal*, vol. 76, no. 2, 2024, pp. 197-222, MLA International Bibliography with Full Text, <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=mlf&AN=202434596870&site=ehost-live&scope=site>

Antoszek, Patrycja. "Haunting Feelings: Shirley Jackson and the Politics of Affect." *Women's Studies*, vol. 49, no. 8, 2020, pp. 850-67, doi:10.1080/00497878.2020.1814292.

Belling, Catherine. "Ghost Meat: Horror, Trauma, and Visceral History." *English Language Notes*, vol. 59, no. 2, 2021, pp. 66-80, MLA International Bibliography with Full Text, doi:10.1215/00138282-9277271.

Berlant, Lauren Gail. *Cruel Optimism*. Duke University Press, 2011.

- Bradway, Tyler. "Queer Exuberance: The Politics of Affect in Jeanette Winterson's Visceral Fiction." *Mosaic: An Interdisciplinary Critical Journal*, vol. 48, no. 1, 2015, pp. 183-200, MLA International Bibliography with Full Text, <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=mlf&AN=2015392328&site=ehost-live&scope=site>
- Brennan, Teresa. *The Transmission of Affect*. Cornell University Press, 2014.
- Briefel, Aviva. "'Freaks of Furniture': The Useless Energy of Haunted Things." *Victorian Studies: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Social, Political, and Cultural Studies*, vol. 59, no. 2, 2017, pp. 209-34, MLA International Bibliography with Full Text, doi:10.2979/victorianstudies.59.2.01.
- Chisholm, Dianne. "Kathy Acker's Grave Songs and Visceral Insights." *Parallax*, vol. 11, no. 3 [36], 2005, pp. 40-54, MLA International Bibliography with Full Text, doi:10.1080/13534640500133963.
- Cixous, Hélène; Cohen, Keith; Cohen, Paula. "The Laugh of the Medusa." *Signs*, vol. 1, no. 4, 1976, pp. 875-93.
- Claas, Monika. "The Visceral Novel Reader and Medicine in Georgian Britain." *Literature and Medicine*, vol. 34, no. 2, 2016, pp. 341-69.
- Fitzgibbons, Moira. "Critical Pleasure, Visceral Literacy, and the Prik of Conscience." *Pedagogy: Critical Approaches to Teaching Literature, Language, Composition, and Culture*, vol. 13, no. 2, 2013, pp. 245-66, MLA International Bibliography with Full Text, doi:10.1215/15314200-1958440.
- Khanna, Neetu. *The Visceral Logics of Decolonization*. Duke University Press, 2020.
- Kristeva, Julia. "Powers of Horror : An Essay on Abjection." *Pouvoirs de l'horreur*, 1982.
- Mergenthal, Silvia. "Visceral Music. The Female Composer in Bernard Maclaverty's Grace Notes." *Anglistik und Englischunterricht*, vol. 81, 2012, pp. 225-39, MLA International Bibliography with Full Text, <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=mlf&AN=2013310032&site=ehost-live&scope=site>.
- Nadiminti, Kalyan. "Infectious Sovereignty: Australian Offshore Detention and Viscerality in Behrouz Boochani's Asylum Art." *The Routledge Companion to Postcolonial and Decolonial Literature*, edited by Praseeda Gopinath and Laura Brueck, Routledge, 2024, pp. 188-203. *Routledge Literature Companions*, MLA International Bibliography with Full Text, <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=mlf&AN=202434676773&site=ehost-live&scope=site>.
- Ngai, Sianne. *Ugly Feelings*. 1 ed., Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2005.
- Ralph, Iris. "Ecofeminist Climate Fiction: Merlinda Bobis's Locust Girl." *Dystopias and Utopias on Earth and Beyond*, edited by Douglas A. Valock, 1 ed., vol. 1, Routledge, 2021, pp. 67-80.
- Saraf, Aanchal. "Aloha Made: The Circulation of Empire, Plastic, and the Visceral in Bishop Museum's 'Unreal Hawai'i'." *Women & Performance: A Journal of Feminist Theory*, vol. 30, no. 1, 2020, pp. 48-69, MLA International Bibliography with Full Text, doi:10.1080/0740770X.2020.1791391.
- Sasser, Kim. *Magical Realism and Cosmopolitanism : Strategizing Belonging*. Palgrave Macmillan, 2014.
- Shildrick, Margrit. "Visceral Phenomenology: Organ Transplantation, Identity, and Bioethics." *Feminist Phenomenology and Medicine*, edited by Kristin Zeiler and Lisa Käll Folkmarson, SUNY Press, 2014, eBook Collection (EBSCOhost), <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=nlebk&AN=706804&site=ehost-live&scope=site>.
- Zeiler, Kristin and Lisa Käll Folkmarson. "Why Feminist Phenomenology and Medicine?" *Feminist Phenomenology and Medicine*, edited by Kristin Zeiler and Lisa Käll Folkmarson, SUNY Press, 2014, eBook Collection (EBSCOhost),

[https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=nlebk&AN=706804&site=ehost-live&scope=site.](https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=nlebk&AN=706804&site=ehost-live&scope=site)